

Optimization Of Digital Theater Art Laboratory For Effective Performance

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ABSTRACT

The study looked at optimization of digital theater art laboratory for effective performance. The study employed the descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design is one in which field samples and data are collected through the aid of a questionnaire. The population consists of one hundred (100) art lecturers in various tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The entire population was adopted as sample for the study. The study develops an instrument titled “Optimization of Digital Theatre Art Laboratory for Effective Performance” (ODTALEP). The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by an expert in the department of Art in Niger Delta University. A reliability coefficient value of 0.83 was obtained from the study. The data obtained from the study will be analyzed using simple mean for the research questions. The data obtained from the hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings obtained from research question 1, table 1, showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. The study showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.45, 3.76, and 3.88 respectively. This shows that deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce organization and time management skills, reduce analytical mind skills, reduce flexibility skills and reduce networking skills. Findings obtained from research question 2, table 2 showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 were all accepted to the various questions. This implies that item 5, 6, 7 and 8 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.44, 3.21 and 3.20 respectively. This shows that deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce memorization skills in display, reduce interpretational skills in drama, reduce observational skills and will reduce critical thinking skills. Findings obtained from research question 3, table 3 showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 were all accepted to the various questions. The findings also revealed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 had a mean value of 3.45, 3.93, 3.67 and 3.56 respectively. This indicates that deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low enrolment of students in classroom activities, creates low participation of students in classroom activities, creates low cooperation of students in classroom project activities and creates low values of students in classroom activities. Findings obtained from table 4 showed that r-calculated value of 1.734 is greater than r-tabulated value of 0.666 at 0.05 level of significance at 7 degree of freedom. Therefore, it was stated that there is a significant correlation between deficiencies of use of digital art on students’ practical skill development and deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. It was finally recommended amongst others that tertiary institutions should adopt recommended standards in equipping digital art theatre laboratories.

Keywords: Optimization, Digital, Theater, Art, Laboratory, Performance

INTRODUCTION

In the present 21st century the world is moving on the pace of advance technology. The educational system had set its research base on the use and application of modern technology tools and equipment. The contemporary digital age is full of participatory opportunity, as it forges great links among personalities as well as groups, such as organizations or nation at large. This great opportunity opens up new chances for growth and development. Not only do we engage with different corners of the world from our own home, but the media itself is entangled with every part of life. Yet, this ease in making contact, and the transformation and participatory opportunity that come with it brings new demands and considerations to life.

As argued by Balme, (2014), we are still searching for ways to describe the entire positive and negative, potentially destructive experiences of digital existence, meaning human experience of life in and with media. However, there is no shortage of interest to seek solutions and to teach about these new possibilities. As stated by scholarship, the contemporary digital age is complex, and poses a challenge not only in how to describe it, in different contexts, but equally to participate and engage in it (Balme, 2014). The system of technology change in most third world countries has affected their educational system in terms of meeting up with global demands. There is a lack of a understanding in the digital age on what its transformations and demands mean for different stakeholders, but these and more scholars offer entry-points that can be built on. While filter bubbles and private-public ownership are examples of popular areas of research and debate on today's media climate, that can engage in political, cultural, and economic perspectives, essential and existential perspectives around the lived experience in different contexts and to different stakeholders, in and with the media, sometimes go unnoticed. One example of a research critique against these popular debates is their focus on economic perspectives (Appelgren, 2008). In contrast, this thesis stays with the individual from a practitioner perspective. Digital existence, which is a term that stems from existential media studies, is an approach in media scholarship that approaches the media research questions from the human experience rather than the media material. In doing so it focuses the exploration and analysis on both digital capabilities and lived experiences – with intent to identify challenges and possibilities in digital existence, and ways to reflect on them. Previous research in existential media studies has, thus far, primarily focused on digital-human vulnerabilities and classic existential themes of death, grief, and ill-health (Blake, 2014).

Drama and Theatre have remained one of the basic tools for exploring and expressing human feelings and predicaments. This is because, theatre is a collaborative art; rich in history and it speaks to our contemporary society since it mirrors human emotions, morality, and fantasy. As a result, all cultures have one form of theatre or the other. Being a fundamental human activity, it involves people working together in order to communicate ideas and also explore social issues to help people respond to various situations affecting them. Be that as it may, it demands discipline and dedication. These facets make it both a delight and a challenge thereby making it an academic discipline that must be studied. The theatre teacher education sequence in Colleges of Education is dedicated to preparing highly qualified artists/teachers to meet the challenges of teaching in the primary and junior secondary school levels. As a theatre student teacher, you receive a solid foundation of basic skills in traditional theatre courses such as acting, directing, design, theatre history and dramatic literature, choreography and technical theatre. At the same time, you will follow a course of instruction specifically focused on teaching theatre at the secondary level. The Theatre Arts Department mounted in Colleges of Education enhances the teaching skills via professional studies taught to students. This is because, at that level of education, the teaching of theatre is done in addition to the general preoccupation of teacher training in the college. This is why these categories of artists are also professional teachers. Theatre workshop occupies a central position in the curriculum of Theatre Arts both in Colleges of Education and Universities. This is because; the workshop class provides an opportunity for students as well as teachers to translate in practical terms the things that are taught theoretically. The workshop class for Theatre Arts students can be likened to the laboratory class for science students. To a large extent, the knowledge of theatrical production is dependent on what

is done during theatre workshop. As a result, the play or material to be acted or performed must be selected with maximum care. This is why Gordon Vallins in his essay titled; “Drama and Theatre in Education” observes that, “Any attempt to stage ‘the School Play’ as an exercise in itself has limited value. It should be regarded as part of a wider project so that the presentation is the result of exploration and research into theme, background, character and time”. Unfortunately, theatre workshop has experienced different challenges in different tertiary institutions. These challenges have affected the effective teaching and learning of Theatre Arts thereby affecting the training of theatre teachers in Colleges of Education. Most of these challenges are administratively inclined; making teaching and learning intricate.

Statement of the Problem

Most institution practice theatre art using the crude method of practice. The analogue system is greatly used by students in most institutions to practice. There is the need to migrate from the analogue system to digital systems through optimisation of practical materials to enhance learning and perfection.

Purpose of the Study

The objective of the study is to expose the deficiency of the use of digital theatre art laboratory for students practice and efficiency in various institutions in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the effect of deficiency of use of digital art on students practical skill development in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.
2. Ascertain the effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.
3. Find out the effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory on students interest in learning and practice in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed and used for the study:

1. What is the effect of deficiency of use of digital art on students’ practical skill development in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?
3. What is the effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory on students’ interest in learning and practice in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

There is no correlation between deficiencies of use of digital art on students’ practical skill development and deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to the deficiency of the use of digital theatre art laboratory for students practice and efficiency in various institutions in Bayelsa State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Access and Cultural Participation

In a recent study, Bryman, (2018) review “the Taking Part Survey data on digital media and cultural participation in the United Kingdom between 2005/2006 and 2015/2016” to assess the effects of digital media on cultural participation in museums and galleries, which they state is “a segment of the cultural sector which has a long history of engagement with digital technology”. Their study is included in this study’s chapter on previous research for this specific reason, as it resonates similarly with experiences in theater of a long history of engagement with digital technology. Also, their study states that it reviews digital optimism in context of “household internet access and use of museum and gallery websites” and “an increase in the diversity of both online and offline audiences”. The optimism, they write, is grounded

in part in government policy, e.g., it is about capabilities, the “capacity to ‘drive our cultural sector’s global status and the engagement, diversity and wellbeing of audiences’” (Department for Digital, Cultural, Media and Sports. While this policy statement may sound good, Buchanan, (2015) conclude that “rather than helping increase the diversity of audiences, online access seems to reproduce, if not enlarge, existing inequalities”. E.g., while diversity has long been a focus in government policy 14 for the arts and cultural sector alongside the simultaneous broader societal developments over the last several decades, as seen regarding both broadcasting and digital media, they state that this has not rendered more equal distribution of arts and culture. Bourdieu, (1984) explain this by referencing the patterns around “cultural capital”, as explained by Bourdieu (1984) that “find clear differences in cultural tastes between people belonging to different socioeconomic classes” (Becker, 1966)

Every theatre laboratory has its goals that it seeks to achieve. Basically, a conventional theatre workshop seeks to achieve a theatrical production be it drama, dance-drama, dance, etc. this is in fact the essence of a workshop experience. However, depending on the circumstances, environment and purpose of theatre workshop, it can have a variety of goals and objectives which it seeks to achieve in addition to the production of the theatre material in question. This research sees the following as cardinal goals of theatre workshop outside producing what is rehearsed in Colleges of Education.

They include:

1. To promote student’s critical thinking through the medium of theatre. By introducing the students to provocative and challenging theatre experiences and fostering their understanding of discussion of performances, theatre workshop aims at enriching young people’s visual, textual and critical literacy. This is achieved through viva during workshop where productions are dissected for critical analysis and understanding.
2. To increase participation in performing arts. By engaging students in the collaborative process of theatre production and offering them the opportunity to connect theatre to their own coursework and life, theatre workshop hopes to increase youth attendance at, involvement in and advocacy for performing arts.
3. To promote the spirit of teamwork. By including students in meaningful conversations among themselves, theatre workshop hopes to grow meaningful relationships with each other and encourage them to think of each other as resourceful and creative persons to learn from and rely on when the need arises; thereby fostering team spirit.

Theatre workshop will lose its relevance and place in the curriculum and teaching of Theatre Arts if it is not functional. This is because, the workshop process is so demanding, involving and encompassing thereby making it the meeting point of all the arts of theatre. Fundamentally, theatre workshop is functional in the following ways:

1. Enables students to develop interpersonal skills such as confidence, social interaction, responsibility sharing, planning, decision making, team spirit/work and problem sharing.
2. Provides high quality professional training in the performing arts.
3. Introduces young people to new and innovative elements of performing arts as well as embracing more traditional performances and practices.
4. Serves local communities by remaining aware of local issues and community needs.
5. Creates opportunities for social and educational development through participation in the arts.

Most theatre workshop sessions begin with warm up games to get the students in the right frame of mind and to loosen up their body. These could be in form of juggling, stilt walking, unicycle, plate spinning, acrobatics etc. According to Leigh High bridge, beginning a workshop session with physical warm-up based on the Alexander Technique can yield good result. According to him, “It entails a series of stretches to elongate the spine, and move the body’s ball joints. Every movement based on the Alexander Technique requires that the actor maintains constant awareness of their spine, and what direction it is moving. Every stretch, even standing erect must be done in the context of widening and lengthening the spine”. It is usually better to conclude the physical warm-up with diaphragmatic

breathing and vocal exercises. This is to bring about harmony between the body and the voice to meet the physical requirement of workshop classes. More importantly, these exercises play a major role in fostering concentration and keeping the body fit for any action. In carrying out theatre workshop for students in tertiary institutions, there is every need to clearly identify the goals and objectives of the workshop to be able to work towards realizing them. This is because; theatre is an enormous discipline that houses different art forms.

METHODS

The study employed the descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design is one in which field samples and data are collected through the aid of a questionnaire. Response options are available for respondents to tick. The study follow suit by developing research instrument in the form of a questionnaire which are handed over to the respondents in the field. It is on this premises that the study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population consists of one hundred (100) art lecturers in various tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The entire population was adopted as sample for the study.

The study develops an instrument titled “Optimization of Digital Theatre Art Laboratory for Effective Performance” (ODTALEP). The instrument is a four point rating scale consisting of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The response options are weighed as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument consists of a total of twelve (12) items on the table.

The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by an expert in the department of Art in Niger Delta University. The expert checked the language structure of the research questions, purpose of the study and the general arrangement for the instrument of the study. Test-retest method was employed to obtain the reliability of the instrument. After administering the same test items to 5 lecturers within two weeks interval, their scores were computed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. A reliability coefficient value of 0.83 was obtained from the study. The data obtained from the study will be analyzed using simple mean for the research questions. The data obtained from the hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question One

What is the effect of deficiency of use of digital art on students’ practical skill development in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Effect of deficiency of use of digital art on students’ practical skill development in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
1	Deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce organization and time management skills	3.44	Accept
2	Deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce analytical mind skills	3.45	Accept
3	Deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce flexibility skills	3.76	Accept
4	Deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce networking skills	3.88	Accept
	Total	14.53	

Findings obtained from research question 1, table 1, showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. The study showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.45, 3.76, and 3.88 respectively. This shows that deficiency of use of digital art on students’ will reduce organization and time management skills, reduce analytical mind skills, reduce flexibility skills and reduce networking skills.

Research Question Two

What is the effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
5	Deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce memorization skills in display	3.44	Accept
6	Deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce interpretational skills in drama	3.44	Accept
7	Deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce observational skills	3.21	Accept
8	Deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce critical thinking skills	3.20	Accept
	Total	13.29	

Findings obtained from research question 2, table 2 showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 were all accepted to the various questions. This implies that item 5, 6, 7 and 8 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.44, 3.21 and 3.20 respectively. This shows that deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce memorization skills in display, reduce interpretational skills in drama, reduce observational skills and will reduce critical thinking skills.

Research Question Three: *What is the effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory on students interest in learning and practice in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?*

Table 3: Effect of deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory on students' interest in learning and practice in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
9	Deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low enrolment of students in classroom activities.	3.45	Accept
10	Deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low participation of students in classroom activities	3.93	Accept
11	Deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low cooperation of students in classroom project activities	3.67	Accept
12	Deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low values of students in classroom activities	3.56	Accept
	Total	14.61	

Findings obtained from research question 3, table 3 showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 were all accepted to the various questions. The findings also revealed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 had a mean value of 3.45, 3.93, 3.67 and 3.56 respectively. This indicates that deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low enrolment of students in classroom activities, creates low participation of students in classroom activities, creates low cooperation of students in classroom project activities and creates low values of students in classroom activities.

Hypothesis

There is no correlation between deficiencies of use of digital art on students' practical skill development and deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

Table 4: correlation between deficiencies of use of digital art on students' practical skill development and deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	X(deficiencies of use of digital art on students' practical skill development)	Y(deficiency of use of digital theater arts laboratory on cognitive achievement)	X ²	Y ²	XY
1	3.44	3.44	11.83	11.83	11.83
2	3.45	3.44	11.90	11.83	11.87
3	3.76	3.21	14.14	10.31	12.07
4	3.88	3.20	15.05	10.24	12.42
	Σ=14.53	Σ=13.29	Σ=52.92	Σ=44.21	Σ=48.19

Findings obtained from table 4 showed that r-calculated value of 1.734 is greater than r-tabulated value of 0.666 at 0.05 level of significance at 7 degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was rejected based on the decision rule. Therefore, it was stated that there is a significant correlation between deficiencies of use of digital art on students' practical skill development and deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings obtained from research question 1, table 1, showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. The study showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.45, 3.76, and 3.88 respectively. This shows that deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce organization and time management skills, reduce analytical mind skills, reduce flexibility skills and reduce networking skills. This is in line with the opinion of Balme,(2014) that suggested that the lack of use of digital laboratory had affected students practical lessons negatively.

Findings obtained from research question 2, table 2 showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 were all accepted to the various questions. This implies that item 5, 6, 7 and 8 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.44, 3.21 and 3.20 respectively. This shows that deficiency of use of digital art on students' will reduce memorization skills in display, reduce interpretational skills in drama, reduce observational skills and will reduce critical thinking skills. According to Blake, (2014) the deficiency in learning experienced by students is caused by lack of art laboratory.

Findings obtained from research question 3, table 3 showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 were all accepted to the various questions. The findings also revealed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 had a mean value of 3.45, 3.93, 3.67 and 3.56 respectively. This indicates that deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory creates low enrolment of students in classroom activities, creates low participation of students in classroom activities, creates low cooperation of students in classroom project activities and creates low values of students in classroom activities. According to Buchanan, (2015) most institutions do not have art laboratories to boast students participation in practical training.

Findings obtained from table 4 showed that r-calculated value of 1.734 is greater than r-tabulated value of 0.666 at 0.05 level of significance at 7 degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was rejected based on the decision rule. Therefore, it was stated that there is a significant correlation between deficiencies of use of digital art on students' practical skill development and deficiency of use of digital theatre arts laboratory on cognitive achievement of students in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Appelgren, (2008) affirmed that when an institution do not have adequate practical equipment for art laboratory both cognitive and affective skill will not be built up among students in the department.

CONCLUSION

In all, the study showed that the deficiency of use of digital art on students' affects their practical skill development in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Also, the deficiency of use of digital theatre arts

laboratory affects students' cognitive achievement in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Further, the deficiency of use of digital theatre art laboratory affects students' interest in learning and practice in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings obtained from the study, it was recommended that:

1. Tertiary institutions should adopt recommended standards in equipping digital art theatre laboratories.
2. Constant reports should be made to the school management to replace worn out facility and upgrade the theatre art laboratory in most tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

REFERENCES

- Appelgren, E. (2008). Konvergens. Berglez, P. & Olausson, U. (red.), I Mediesamhället. Centrala Begrepp. Lund: *Studentlitteratur AB*.
- Auslander, P. (2008). Liveness: Performance in a mediatized culture. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203938133>
- Balme, C. B. (2014). The theatrical public sphere. New York: *Cambridge University Press*.
- Becker, S.L. (1966) The role of theatre in our society: Implications for school curricula, *The Speech Teacher*, 15:2, 126-131, DOI: 10.1080/03634526609377507
- Blake, B. (2014). Theater & The Digital. *Palgrave McMillan*.
- Bryman, A. (2018). Samhällsvetenskapliga metoder, 3rd ed. *Liber*.
- Bourdieu, P. (1984) Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste. Cambridge, MA: *Harvard University Press*.
- Buchanan, I. (2015) Assemblage Theory and Its Discontents. *Deleuze Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.3366/dls.2015.0193>